

Damage to double layer truss roof supported by RC columns for the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake in Japan

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate damage to the double layer truss roof supported by RC columns subjected to the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake in Japan. Its structural analysis is carried out to confirm the reason why the damage occurred as well. The concourse roof of the building is a cylindrical spatial truss structure supported by RC pillars. The column bases of the spatial truss roof are connected to the RC support columns via anchor bolts in the base plates. The damage is as follows: In the longitudinal direction, a rigidity difference occurred due to the varying heights of the support columns. This caused the concrete directly beneath the base plates of the shorter, and thus more rigid, columns to spall. A large number of these spalled concrete pieces fell to the first-floor level. The support column slopes downward toward the west, making this the shortest column. It is also the column with the greatest rigidity among the support columns. The study results in the cause of the damage due to the imbalance bending rigidity of the support columns such as the columns height.

Keywords: 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake, double-layer spatial truss roof, support section, damage investigation, lateral failure, concrete, and static elastic analysis.

1. Introduction

During the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake, damage such as cracking and spalling of mortar and concrete occurred at the support sections of a two-layer spatial truss roof structure. The construction site of this structure recorded a seismic intensity of 6 lower on the Japanese seismic scale. The support sections of the two-layer spatial truss roof structure are installed at the column heads of RC support columns, which are supported by the rooftops of four RC multi-layer structures.

In this study, the damage to the support sections of this roof structure, which was affected by the earthquake, is analyzed and examined based on damage survey images and static elastic analysis. Specifically, the study aims to clarify the seismic response amplification factor of this roof structure, the seismic forces acting on it that led to lateral failure of the support sections, and other related factors. Furthermore, this research provides insights and lessons on preventing the detachment of mortar and concrete at the support sections of such spatial structures, as well as the impact of stiffness variations on their seismic response.

2. Building overview and damage conditions

The building overview is shown in Fig. 1, and an interior view from the concourse is provided in Fig. 2. As observed in Figs. 1 and 2, the support columns extend from the rooftops of four RC multi-layer structures. The seismic motion propagates from the ground to the RC multi-layer structures and then to the RC support columns extending from their rooftops. Consequently, due to this complex transmission path, significant amplification of the seismic response in the roof structure is anticipated. Furthermore, variations in the length and arrangement of the support columns lead to differences in the stiffness of the substructure, which is expected to have a considerable impact on the seismic response of the roof

structure. The damaged support sections are marked with square symbols in Fig. 3 and are located at (X1, Y3), (X5, Y3), and (X7, Y3), hereinafter referred to as N1, N5, and N6, respectively.

Figure 1: Building overview (The red lines indicate the columns.) Figure 2: Interior View of the Concourse

The affected building is a multifunctional facility designed to cover the concourse with the roof structure supported by RC support columns extending from the rooftops of each RC building. The dimensions of the roof structure are approximately 12.0 m in span direction and 92.5 m in longitudinal direction. The roof framing plan and elevation views are presented in Fig. 4.

Figure3: Structural layout plan and framing elevation (Unit: mm)

Roof truss layout plan

Roof Truss Framing Elevation (Y3 Grid)

Figure 4: Damage condition of the support section (Unit: mm)

Fig. 5 illustrates the detailed configuration of the support sections. The base mortar at each support section has a thickness of approximately 130 mm.

According to the earthquake damage investigation, the following observations were made:

N1: Cracking and spalling were observed in both the concrete and base mortar of the support section, which were associated with lateral failure of the anchor bolts.

N5 and N6: Cracking and spalling of the base mortar at the support sections were attributed to the bearing failure of anchor bolts due to bending moments.

RC structural frames and roof steel frames: No damage was observed.

Base plates at N1, N2, and N3: Displacement in the north-south direction was confirmed in Fig. 6.

Truss roof displacement: Based on the anchor bolt positions at N1 and N2, it is inferred that the truss roof shifted southward.

Figure 5: Detailed drawing of the support section of column N1 (X1, Y3) (Unit: mm)

Figure 6: Movement of the base plate

Analytical model and applied seismic force

Since no significant damage was observed outside the support sections of the columns during the earthquake damage investigation, a static elastic analysis was conducted by modeling the roof structure and support columns. The truss steel tubes of the roof structure were assumed to have an outer diameter of 101.6 mm and thickness of 5.0mm made of steel. Fig. 7 presents an overview of the analytical model and Table 1 provides the geometric specifications of the roof structure.

Figure 7. Analysis model

Table 1. Shape of the Three-Dimensional Truss Roof Structure

Spatial truss roof	X	Span Lx(m)	12
		Half open angle $\theta_x(^{\circ})$	0
		Carvature radius Rx(m)	0
	Z	Span Lz(m)	92.5
		Half open angle $\theta_z(^{\circ})$	10.5
		Carvature radiu Rz(m)	254
		Depth dr(m)	1.8
		Span-depth ratio	51.3
		Rise h(m)	4.2

In the analytical model, the column bases were assumed to be fixed supports, while the support sections of the spatial truss roof and the column heads were modeled as pinned supports. A three-dimensional frame analysis program, Multiframe, was used to perform the static elastic analysis.

The applied seismic load Q_i was determined using the following equation:

$$Q_i = W \cdot C_0 \quad (1)$$

where:

W : Self-weight of the structure

C_0 : Standard shear force coefficient (set to 0.2 as the basic seismic force in this study)

The self-weight of the structure (W) was assumed to be 1 kN/m² per unit area, resulting in a total of 758 kN. The calculated seismic force was then distributed among the nodes of the spatial truss and applied as horizontal forces.

Analysis results and bearing capacity of the support sections

Analysis results

The member lengths of each support column are shown in Fig. 8, and their rigidity and rigidity ratios are presented in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively. The response shear forces of each support column, obtained through static elastic analysis by applying the prescribed seismic loads to the nodes of the analytical model, are illustrated in Fig. 11.

Figure 8: Member lengths of each support column

Figure 9: Rigidity of each support column

For the rigidity ratio k of the northern support columns (N1–N11), the rigidity of column N1, which exhibited the highest rigidity K among the northern columns, was used as the standard rigidity K_0 . Similarly, the rigidity ratio k of the southern support columns (S1–S11) was calculated using the rigidity of column S11, which had the highest rigidity among the southern columns, as the reference K_0 . From Fig. 11, it can be observed that significant shear forces were generated in N1 and N6, the two columns that experienced the most severe damage. Additionally, the shear force in S11 was considerably higher

than that in other southern support columns. This phenomenon can be attributed to the higher rigidity ratio of S11 compared to the other southern columns, as indicated in Fig. 10(b).

Figure 10: Rigidity of each support column

Figure 11: Response shear force of each column ($C_0 = 0.2$)

Bearing capacity of the support sections

The bearing capacity of the support sections was calculated by multiplying the lateral failure strength of concrete at the minimum edge distance by the number of anchor bolts. This represents the strength at which all anchors equally share the shear force until failure occurs in the support section, and the anchor at the minimum edge distance reaches lateral failure.

The lateral failure mechanism of the support section is illustrated in Fig. 12, and the equations used to compute the bearing capacity are provided below.

$$Q_s = q \cdot n \quad (2)$$

where:

Q_s : Bearing capacity of the support section

q : Lateral failure strength of an anchor bolt

n : Number of anchor bolts (set as $n=2$ in this study)

$$q = \varphi \cdot \sigma \cdot A \quad (3)$$

$$A = 0.5\pi c^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma = 0.31\sqrt{Fc} \quad (5)$$

where:

ϕ : Reduction factor (short-term: 2/3)

σ : Tensile strength of concrete under cone-shaped failure

A : Effective projected area of the lateral failure surface in the shear force direction

c : Edge distance (set as 160 mm in this study)

F_c : Design compressive strength of concrete (21 N/mm²)

Using Equation (2), the bearing capacity of the support section is calculated as: $Q_s = 76.2 \text{ kN}$

Figure 12: Lateral failure of column concrete (q, c, L, A)

Analysis and discussion of damage factors

The damage conditions of columns N1, N5, and N6 observed in this earthquake are shown in Fig. 13. From these observations: N1 exhibited lateral failure of concrete, N5 and N6 exhibited bearing failure of mortar.

Column N1

Column N5

Column N6

Figure 13: Damage condition of the bearing section

Column N1

To evaluate the column proportions, the member length h was divided by the column base width D . The column proportions for each support column are presented in Fig. 14. The proportion of N1 was 1.2, indicating that N1 is a short column when considering the bending restraint at the support section. Based on this, the support section likely experienced lateral failure due to shear force. Using the bearing capacity of the support section $Q_s = 76.2 \text{ kN}$, the seismic force P_s acting on the node of the roof structure required to cause lateral failure at the support section was calculated. The formula for P_s is as follows:

$$P_s = C_0 \frac{Q_s}{Q} P_d \quad (6)$$

where:

P_d = Nodal vertical load calculated based on unit load (1 kN/m²)

Q : Shear force acting on column N1 (obtained from the analysis using the seismic load from Eq. (1))

The seismic intensity C_s at which lateral failure of the support section occurs is calculated as follows:

$$C_s = C_0 \frac{Q_s}{Q} = 0.2 \frac{Q_s}{Q} \quad (7)$$

From the observed damage, only N1 experienced concrete lateral failure. Therefore, the shear force Q used to determine C_s was taken from N1. This results in a seismic intensity $C_s = 1.2$. Fig. 15 illustrates the shear forces acting on each support section at the moment of lateral failure, determined using C_s . Next, using $C_s = 1.2$, the response amplification factor R_s of the roof structure was calculated. The observed peak ground acceleration (PGA) was 340 cm/s², and the equation used to determine R_s is as follows:

$$R_s = \frac{C_s \cdot 980}{PGA} = \frac{980}{340} C_s \quad (8)$$

Using this equation, $R_s = 3.5$ was obtained. From the analysis results, as shown in Figure 15, the largest response shear force among all support columns occurred at N1, leading to its lateral failure.

Figure 14: Column proportions

Figure 15: Response shear force of each column ($C_0 = 1.2$)

The shear force borne by each column is significantly influenced by the stiffness ratio. Columns with higher stiffness ratios tend to bear greater shear forces. The horizontal stiffness of each column was evaluated using the following formula, assuming the columns as cantilever beams:

$$K = \frac{3EI}{h^3} \quad (9)$$

where:

E : Young's modulus, I : Second moment of area, h : Column length

From this equation, shorter column lengths result in higher stiffness and greater shear force distribution. As shown in Figs 8, 9, and 10, N1 has the shortest column length and the highest stiffness among all columns. This suggests that N1 bore a significant shear force, leading to lateral failure. Furthermore, as indicated by the analysis results and Fig. 15, the shear force acting on the N1 support section exceeded its bearing capacity, confirming the cause of failure.

Column N5

The column proportion of N5 was determined as $h/D = 3.6$. Based on Fig. 13, the failure of N5's support section appears to be due to bearing failure caused by bending moments. The bearing failure mechanism is illustrated in Figure 16, while the governing area of each column is presented in Fig. 17. The damage to N5 is presumed to be primarily influenced by its governing area. While the basic governing area for columns N2, N3, and N4 is 2 grid units, the governing area for N5 is 2.5 grid units. Consequently, N5 bore greater shear forces compared to N2, N3, and N4, leading to more severe damage.

Column N6

The column proportion of N6 was determined as $h/D=2.6$. Based on the damage photographs, N6 exhibited bearing failure at the support section, similar to N5, likely due to bending moments. The analysis results suggest that the governing area was the primary cause of this damage, similar to N5.

As shown in Fig. 17, the governing area for N6 is 3.5 grid units, significantly larger than that of other columns. As a result, N6 bore greater shear forces and sustained more severe damage compared to columns N2, N3, and N4.

Failure mode diagram

Column damage condition

Figure 16: concrete bearing failure due to anchor bolt pull-out force caused by bending moment

Figure 17: Governing area of each column (Unit: Grid)

Countermeasures against falling due to base mortar and concrete delamination

The most significant damage to the spatial structure was the delamination of concrete and base mortar. The detached concrete and mortar fell from a height of approximately 10 m. Fig. 18 shows the concrete and mortar debris that fell onto the concourse's first-floor surface.

Figure 18: Concrete and mortar fallen from the bearing section of the damaged column

To prevent similar damage in the future, the following countermeasures are proposed:

Reinforcing the mortar and concrete beneath the base plate of the support section by wrapping them with steel plates or similar materials. Enhancing the shear strength of RC column support sections to prevent collapse and falling. Since these reinforcement methods directly contribute to life safety, it is strongly recommended that they be implemented as preventive measures.

Conclusion

This study focused on a two-layer spatial truss roof supported by RC columns and conducted an earthquake damage investigation and static elastic analysis. The following findings were obtained as follows. Cracks and delamination were observed in the concrete and base mortar of the support sections due to lateral failure of anchor bolts. However, no damage was observed in the RC structure or the spatial truss roof. Significant shear forces acted on the RC column support sections, leading to damage. Moving forward, it is essential to accurately evaluate the shear forces acting on support sections and ensure they have sufficient bearing capacity. By doing so, improvements in seismic performance can be achieved, along with preventative measures against the falling of concrete and mortar.

References

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